

Sol-gel TiO₂-based coatings in 3D printed porous Ti-6Al-4V alloy structures as efficient antibacterial drug delivery systems: Thorough structural and biological characterization.

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Abstract

The application of sol-gel coatings on titanium-based materials offers a promising approach for enhancing their bioactivity, antibacterial properties, and adhesion, particularly for biomedical applications. This study focuses, for the first time, on the preparation and characterization of sol-gel TiO₂-based coatings containing hydroxyapatite and silver in 3D-printed porous gyroid and dodecahedral structures. TiO₂-based coatings on the standard wrought Ti-6Al-4V alloy rods were used as a reference. The coatings were applied via the specific dip-coating process developed by the author team. The microstructural analysis revealed that the sol-gel coatings on the reference wrought rod samples were homogeneous and well-adhered. The coatings on the porous gyroid and dodecahedral structures exhibited some localized cracking due to the complex geometry of the porous structures. Bioactivity was evaluated through the standard *in vitro* simulated body fluid tests, confirming hydroxyapatite precipitation on HA-containing coatings. Antibacterial properties were assessed against *Escherichia coli*, demonstrating nearly 100% bacterial inhibition for Ag-containing coatings. Cytotoxicity tests with L929 fibroblast cells indicated that coatings with lower Ag concentrations in sol were non-toxic, while higher Ag concentrations in sol resulted in reduced cell viability, particularly in gyroid structures.

Keywords: dodecahedral, gyroid, sol-gel coatings, 3D printing, hydroxyapatite, silver

1. Introduction

Sol-gel titania-based coatings applied to Ti-6Al-4V biomedical alloy fabricated via 3D printing represent an emerging area of research, particularly in biomedical and engineering applications. These coatings are primarily utilized to enhance surface properties, including bioactivity, adhesion, corrosion resistance, and antibacterial performance. To date, these coatings have been applied to compact and plane implant surfaces and, to the best of our knowledge, no scientific reports deal with the application of sol-gel titania-based coatings in 3D printed porous structures made of Ti-6Al-4V alloy.

Porous structures, however, show a very high specific surface, so that they could be considered containers for drugs or antibacterial substances.

The advantage of porous, namely gyroid and dodecahedron lattices, is that they closely mimic the architecture of natural trabecular bone [1, 2]. Gyroid structures, as triply periodic minimal surfaces, offer a high surface area-to-volume ratio and excellent mechanical properties [3]. Their biomimetic design facilitates cell attachment and proliferation, making them well-suited for bone scaffold applications [4, 5]. Similarly, dodecahedron (dodethick) structures are complex porous networks widely used in biomedical and mechanical fields due to their high load-bearing capacity and tunable porosity, which contribute to improved mechanical stability, fluid permeability and reduced stress-shielding [6, 7].

The sol-gel process involves the formation of a colloidal suspension (sol), which undergoes gelation to create a three-dimensional network (gel) [8]. This technique enables precise control over the coating's composition, thickness, and surface properties. Titania-based sol-gel coatings are particularly advantageous for biomedical applications, including implants and scaffolds, due to their biocompatibility, osteointegration potential, antibacterial activity and corrosion resistance [9, 10].

The application of sol-gel coatings enhances surface bioactivity and functionality. Coatings doped with hydroxyapatite (HA) and silver nitrate (AgNO_3) can improve bone integration and introduce antibacterial properties, respectively [11]. Post-coating heat treatment enhances adhesion and crystallinity while converting amorphous TiO_2 into its more stable anatase or rutile phase, further improving coating durability and biological performance [12, 13].

Sol-gel coatings on 3D-printed titanium structures promote cell adhesion and proliferation, forming a protective layer against oxidation and degradation [12, 14]. Additionally, silver (Ag) doping provides an antimicrobial effect, helping to prevent post-implantation infections [15].

Several studies conducted at our university have focused on the development and characterization of titanium-based coatings on titanium substrates for biomedical applications. These studies investigated the use of sol-gel and dip-coating techniques to apply coatings containing various additives such as silver, calcium, and phosphate to improve the properties of titanium implants. The coatings were evaluated for their adhesion, antibacterial activity, bioactivity, and cytocompatibility. The results generally showed that these coatings exhibited good adhesion, antibacterial effects against bacteria such as gram-negative *E. coli* and gram-positive *S. epidermidis*, promoted biological activity through the formation of hydroxyapatite, and were nontoxic to cells.

Specifically, some research conducted by our team investigated coatings on porous titanium, TiSi alloys, and the effect of adding calcium titanate powder to sol-gel coatings [16-23]. However, sol-gel coatings on 3D printed and porous materials have not been investigated to date. In fact, the sol-gel technique applied on porous structures with very low pore dimensions is a challenge, as the perfect contact of viscous sol with pore surfaces should be ensured.

The aim of this study was to prepare and characterize sol-gel titania-based coatings, with silver (Ag) and commercial hydroxyapatite (HA, $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$), on three different titanium-based substrates: a Ti-6Al-4V alloy rod, a 3D-printed porous Ti-6Al-4V gyroid structure, and a 3D-printed porous titanium dodethick structure. The prepared coatings

were evaluated in terms of bioactivity and antibacterial effects to assess their potential for biomedical applications.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Sample preparation

The experiment followed the procedure outlined in Figure 1.

The initial substrate for the sol-gel coating was a machined wrought TiAl6V4 alloy rod, 15 mm in diameter and 3 mm in height, with a surface area of 4.94 cm² (Fig. 2). This rod underwent grinding with P400, P600, and P800 grit silicon carbide abrasive papers (grinder Buehler MetaServ 250). Subsequently, the rod was cleaned ultrasonically in ethanol for 10 minutes.

The second substrate for the sol-gel coating was a 3D-printed TiAl6V4 alloy gyroid, 15 mm in diameter and 3 mm in height, with a surface area of 9.90 cm² (Fig. 3). The gyroid was ultrasonically cleaned in ethanol for 3 x 10 minutes.

The third substrate for the sol-gel coating was a 3D-printed titanium dodecahedron (lattice: 1.35), 15 mm in diameter and 3 mm in height, with a surface area of approximately 14 cm² (Fig. 4). The dodecahedron was ultrasonically cleaned in ethanol for 2 x 10 minutes.

2.2. Composition and conditions for the preparation of sols

The basic titanium sol (T sol) was prepared by gradually mixing tetra-n-butyl-orthotitanate (Sigma Aldrich Merck), Triton X-100 (Roth), 1 mol/l HNO₃ (p.a., Lach-Ner), acetylacetone (p.a., Lach-Ner), and ethanol (den.), followed by stirring at laboratory temperature for 24 hours and aging at laboratory temperature for 24 hours. The aged T sol had a viscosity of 4.8 mPas (viscometer RV1). The basic sol was then divided into three 25 ml aliquots: the first aliquot remained unmodified (T sol), AgNO₃ with a silver concentration of 0.04 mol/l was added to the second, and AgNO₃ with a silver concentration of 0.06 mol/l was added to the third. After dissolving the AgNO₃, commercial hydroxyapatite with a concentration of 0.2 mol/l was added to the sols (TAN04HA sol, TAN06HA sol).

A dip-coater (IDLab) (Fig. 5) was used for coating. The dipping speed was 20 cm/min, the withdrawal speed was 6 cm/min, and the dwell time in the sol was 30 seconds, with a sol stirring speed of 200 rpm (IKA). Coating was performed at laboratory temperature.

2.3 Heat treatment conditions for coated substrates

The coated samples were dried at laboratory temperature, placed in holders (Fig. 6), and then heat-treated in air at 400 °C for 120 minutes using a heating rate of 2 °C/min (Clasic). The samples were cooled to room temperature overnight.

2.4 Measurement of the selected properties

The adhesion of the coatings to the machined wrought rod substrate was assessed using an adhesive tape test, according to ASTM D3359-02 [24]. A 6 x 6 grid of scratches was made on the coatings. Following tape application (Permacel 99), loading, and

peeling, the coating surfaces were visually characterized, and the degree of adhesion was determined using a classification scale.

The bioactivity of all coating types on the three substrate types was evaluated according to ISO 23317 [25]. Coated samples (n = 2 per condition) were immersed in a simulated body fluid solution, maintaining a constant surface area-to-volume ratio (S/V), for 21 days at 36.5 °C. The simulated body fluid solution was replaced every 7 days. After the *in vitro* test, the samples were dried at laboratory temperature and characterized.

Using atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS, Agilent 280 FS) the concentration of Ca²⁺ was determined, and UV-VIS (Shimadzu UV-2450) was used to measure the concentration of (PO₄)³⁻ ions in SBF solutions before and after the 21-day *in vitro* test.

The antibacterial activity of the coatings was measured statically in a flow box (SafeFast Elite) for 24 hours at laboratory temperature using *Escherichia coli* (strain DMB3138). The coated substrates were immersed into suspension of physiological solution (NaCl, 9 g.l⁻¹) with bacteria concentration of 10⁴ CFU.ml⁻¹ for 24 hours at the laboratory temperature in the dark. A consistent surface area-to-volume ratio (S/V) was maintained across sample types. Two independent tests were performed. Following the interaction period, 100 µL aliquots of the suspension were taken and spread onto two Petri dishes with agar (LB). Four dishes from each coating and substrate type were incubated in a biological thermostat at 36.5 °C for 24 hours. After incubation, the dishes were photographed, and the colonies of surviving bacteria were counted using the computer program NIS-Elements AR 3.10 and visually compared to the reference sample (suspension without contact with the samples).

Cytotoxicity measurements for all three coating types on both substrate types were performed according to ISO 10993-5 [26]. Samples were sterilized in 70% ethanol for 2 hours. After drying, the samples were immersed in MEM + 5% FBS medium (Minimum Essential Medium, Fetal Bovine Serum) with antibiotics in 50 mL tubes at 37 °C on an orbital shaker (130 rpm) for 24 hours. The extraction ratio was 1.25 cm²/ml. Each material was tested in triplicate. L929 cells (ATCC CCL-1) were seeded in a 96-well plate in MEM + 10% FBS medium (10,000 cells/well) and cultured for 24 hours in an incubator (37 °C, 5% CO₂). After 24 hours, the material extracts were added to the subconfluent cell layer. Six technical replicates (wells) were used for each sample. The extraction medium alone (MEM + 5% FBS with antibiotics) served as the negative control, and the medium with detergent (0.5% Triton X-100) served as the positive (toxic) control. The silver concentration in the extracts was measured using ICP-OES. Following 24 hours of incubation with the extracts, the metabolic activity of the cells was assessed using the resazurin test. The extracts were removed, and a solution of resazurin (final concentration 25 µg/ml) in MEM medium without phenol red was pipetted onto the cells. After 1.5 hours, the fluorescence of the formed resorufin (ex/em 560/590 nm) was measured. The relative metabolic activity was expressed as a percentage of the negative (unaffected) control.

2.5. Characterization of the substrates and coatings

The substrates and coatings before and after tests were characterised by scanning electron microscope (Hitachi S4700, 15 kV, 20 µA) and by the optical microscope (Olympus BX 51).

3. Results

3.1. Microstructure of the prepared samples

For uniformity, the surfaces of the machined wrought TiAl6V4 alloy rods underwent mechanical grinding. However, traces of scratches remained after cleaning. Subsequent cleaning with ethanol revealed small spherical spherulites, ranging from units to tens of micrometers, on the gyroid samples. While the gyroid surface area was calculated based on cell shape and number, electron microscope images showed a larger actual surface area due to the pervasive presence of these spherulites. These surface irregularities may significantly influence the quality and properties of subsequently prepared coatings. Further characterization and testing of these novel gyroid-shaped biomaterials will be essential.

Following ultrasonic cleaning with ethanol, the surfaces of the dodethick substrates displayed 3D-printed grid layers (1.35 mm hole size) arranged in a scaffold structure. The theoretical substrate surface area was calculated from the grid shape (1.35 mm), the number of printed layers, and the wafer shape. However, electron microscope images revealed that the actual surface area was larger than this approximation. This discrepancy was attributed to the presence of inhomogeneously distributed spherical structures (units to tens of micrometers) on the grid layers. These surface irregularities may significantly affect the quality and properties of subsequently prepared coatings.

Following firing, the coatings on the alloy machined shaped bars presented isolated cracks. These cracks did not have a negative impact on the properties measured. The coating are very thin, and perfectly copies the surface of the substrate, as the morphology typical of grinding is visible. The commercial hydroxyapatite particles, with particle sizes in the micrometer range, and the silver particles, with particle sizes in the nanometer range for both concentrations, were distributed relatively homogeneously throughout the coating surface.

Following firing, the coatings on the 3D-printed gyroid alloy exhibited significantly more cracking than those on the machined rod substrates. This increased cracking is likely due to the irregular surface of the gyroid, which hindered uniform coating flow during withdrawal, compared to the smoother rod samples. The presence of a plate/doughnut structure in the lower part of the gyroid sample further contributed to uneven sol flow during withdrawal. However, all coatings accurately replicated the dissected surface of the gyroid, with no significant alteration of its dimensions, indicating optimal sol viscosity. The distribution of commercial hydroxyapatite particles within the coatings was relatively uniform. Conversely, a closer examination revealed an uneven distribution of silver particles in both concentration cases. The thickness of the basic coating (T) was low because small and larger beads of the original gyroid surface were still visible after coating. The coatings with Ag and HA (TAN04HA, TAN06HA) exhibited a significantly greater thickness, as these coatings covered most of the gyroid surface features.

Coatings of the basic T sol applied to the 3D dodethick substrate showed cracking. This is probably due to the irregular surface of the bead grid and the wafer, which resulted in complex coating flow during the extraction process. While cracks were present, the coating remained adhered and precisely replicated the highly structured surface. The coating thickness was visually estimated to be in the range of 350 to 400 nm.

Despite perfectly replicating the substrate's complex surface, the coating containing Ag and HA exhibited an irregular distribution of nano-sized silver (Ag) and micro-sized

hydroxyapatite (HA) particles. The structured surface limited the ability to achieve a homogeneous particle distribution. Cracks were observed in the coating (TAN04HA); however, they did not negatively impact its quality or properties. The coating demonstrated excellent adhesion to the substrate.

Functionally, the TAN06HA coating was comparable to the TAN04HA coating, differing only in its higher Ag concentration. Although local cracks were present, particularly around the HA beads and particles, the coating accurately replicated the grid's structured surface without dimensional changes. An uneven distribution of silver nanoparticles was observed. The coating exhibited high adhesion to the substrate.

Cross-sectional analysis was performed to examine the microstructure of the coating. To assess whether the viscosity of the sols (T, TAN04HA, and TAN06HA) facilitated their penetration through the scaffold lattice to the plate during coating under constant stirring, the coated substrates were sectioned and visually characterized post-firing. Evaluation of both optical microscopy (OM) images and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) details revealed that the coatings precisely replicated the intricate inner surface of the lattice, thus confirming the penetration of all sols to the plate. Hydroxyapatite (HA) particles and silver (Ag) particles were observed within the TAN04HA and TAN06HA coatings inside the coated scaffolds. Interestingly, the coatings showed little evidence of cracking within the substrates. Nevertheless, the concentration and distribution of the incorporated elements (micro-HA, nano-Ag) within the lattice cavities require further investigation.

3.2. Properties of the prepared samples

3.2.1 Adhesion test

The coatings on the alloy samples of the machined wrought rod showed very good adhesion, evaluated according to the classification table as grade 5B (possibly even 4B), see Fig. 16. After visual characterization, it was found that particles of commercial hydroxyapatite and silver (for both concentrations) remained fixed in the coatings after the tape was peeled off. Even some of the adhesive from the tape remained on the sample after it was torn off.

3.2.2 Bioactivity test

The alloy coatings containing commercial hydroxyapatite (TAN04HA, TAN06HA) showed excellent bioactive properties, with a visually detected thick layer of precipitated bone hydroxyapatite (HAp) after the in vitro test. The hydroxyapatite globules, composed of plate-like nanocrystals, grew and clustered with increasing exposure time in SBF. The layer cracked as a result of drying (during preparation for SEM measurements), which allowed for a rough estimation of the layer thickness in the micrometre range. It is important to consider that, in vivo, the layer would not be air-exposed, suggesting that the cracking was induced by laboratory measurements. In comparison, the T coating (without HA and Ag additives) exhibited very low bioactivity, indicated by the precipitation of isolated, very small HAp globules on the coating surface.

The coatings on the 3D gyroid behaved consistently with the coatings on the machined wrought rod. Across all coating types, surface images showed that the layer of precipitated hydroxyapatite faithfully replicated the fired coating, even with cracking present. The nanoplate-like globules presented a consistent structure, with sizes in the

micrometer range. The outer and inner spaces of the gyroid demonstrated uniform behavior throughout the test, with no localized changes in behavior detected, despite the sample's complex geometry.

Dodethick with coating T (base coating without additives) showed no changes after 21 days of exposure in simulated body fluid (SBF) solution. The coating's surface displayed no changes in morphology or composition, and no phases or precipitates were detected. This coating did not demonstrate bioactive properties following *in vitro* testing.

The TAN04HA coating on dodethick, containing lower silver (Ag) and commercial hydroxyapatite (HA) content, showed excellent bioactive properties. At the conclusion of the 21-day *in vitro* test, a visually detected layer of precipitated hydroxyapatite (HAp) was observed, composed of globules of platelet-shaped nanocrystals. This layer experienced cracking due to drying, a procedure necessary for SEM measurements.

The TAN06HA coating on dodethick, containing a higher concentration of silver (Ag) and the same concentration of commercial hydroxyapatite (HA) as the TAN04HA coating, showed similar behavior to the TAN04HA coating. After 21 days of *in vitro* testing in simulated body fluid (SBF), the coated dodethick scaffold surface was almost completely covered with a layer of precipitated hydroxyapatite (HAp). This precipitated phase was characterized by globules composed of platelet-like nanocrystals. Detailed SEM analysis revealed that the precipitated HAp platelets grew directly from the commercial HA particles within the TAN06HA coating. As the *in vitro* testing time increased, the HAp globules (with sizes in the micrometer range) grew and interconnected, forming a continuous layer. This layer completely covered the original coating, filled firing cracks, and filled voids in the scaffold lattice. At low magnification (x30), SEM images showed that the precipitated hydroxyapatite layer perfectly replicated the morphology of the coated scaffold. The HAp nanoplatelet globules exhibited the same structure for both types of coatings (TAN04HA, TAN06HA).

Using AAS, the concentration of Ca^{2+} was determined, and UV-VIS was used to measure the concentration of $(\text{PO}_4)^{3-}$ ions in SBF solutions before and after the 21-day *in vitro* test. For biomaterial predictive testing, monitoring changes in the concentrations and pH of the SBF solution is crucial, along with analysing changes in the composition and structure of the tested samples (OM, SEM). Compared to the reference sample, calcium and phosphate ions decreased by more than 20%. SBF solutions also showed a similar trend in pH values. This decrease in ions from SBF solutions suggests ion uptake from the solution, indicating the precipitation of a calcium-phosphate phase, preferably hydroxyapatite (HAp), and thus demonstrating bioactive properties of the tested biomaterials.

3.2.3 Antibacterial test

The coatings were characterized after 24 hours of antibacterial testing against *E. coli*. After 24-hour interaction of the coated substrates with the bacterial suspension of NaCl + *E. coli*, the samples were discarded and 100 μl of the reacted suspension was plated onto a Petri dish with LB agar. The dishes (four from each type of coating) were photographed after 24-hour incubation. The colonies of surviving bacteria were counted using the computer program NIS-Elements AR 3.10 (see Fig. 22). By comparison with the control, it can be stated that the coatings on the silver-containing alloy showed the almost same

100% antibacterial effect against *E. coli*. Both concentrations in the coatings ensured the death of bacteria after 24 hours of interaction.

After 24 hours of antibacterial testing, the coatings on gyroid 3D scaffolds demonstrated the same effect as those on machined wrought rods. In both cases, complete (99.9%) eradication of *E. coli* colonies was achieved with coatings containing both concentrations of silver (TAN04HA, TAN06HA).

Relative to the control (suspension without contact with samples), the Ti-dodecyl (3D printing; grid: 1.35) scaffolds coated with both silver concentrations (TAN04HA, TAN06HA) showed a 99.6-99.8% reduction in viable *E. coli*, indicating a 99.6-99.8% antibacterial effect against this gram-negative bacteria. *E. coli* bacteria were killed after 24 hours of interaction with the bacterial suspension for both silver concentrations in the coatings. However, the Ti-dodecyl substrate (3D printing; grid: 1.35) coated with a base coating (T) lacking Ag and HA exhibited only a 45% antibacterial effect (Table 1). It is known that the basic TiO₂ coating without additives shows a partial antibacterial effect. The measured values (28 – 45 %) were similar to those of the authors [22, 23, 27].

Table 1 Antibacterial effect [%] of the coatings against *E. coli* after 24-hour antibacterial test (average of four values)

Type of the coating/substrate	Antibacterial effect [%]		
	Rod	Gyroid	DodeThick
T	34	28	45
TAN04HA	100	99.9	99.8
TAN06HA	99.9	99.9	99.6

3.2.4 Cytotoxicity test

The coatings were further characterized using a 24-hour non-contact cytotoxicity test with L929 cells (test on extracts according to ISO standard). The graph depicts the relative metabolic activity (%) of cell line L929 (mouse fibroblasts) after 24 hours of exposure to extracts of the tested samples (rod and gyroid, both with and without coatings). The concentration of silver released from the coatings (TAN04HA, TAN06HA) into the extracts (mg/l) is also presented. The higher silver concentration released from gyroid samples with TAN06HA coatings to the medium demonstrated toxicity – the relative metabolic activity of the cells incubated with the extracts of aforementioned samples was decreased. In contrast, other extracts, irrespective of silver presence (gyroid: T and TAN04HA; rod: T, TAN04HA, and TAN06HA), did not reduce cell metabolic activity below the 70% threshold of the negative (unaffected) control, indicating cytocompatibility. This observation implies that the shape/surface of the samples affects the incorporation of additives within the final sol-gel coatings.

Despite adjusting the extraction ratio to achieve the same surface area to volume ratio (S/V), the silver content in the gyroid extracts was about 5 times higher compared to the rod extracts.

Table 2 The silver content in the extracts

Substrate	Coating	Replica	Ag in extracts (mg·l ⁻¹)
<i>Rod TiAlV</i>	TAN04HA	A	0.570
<i>Rod TiAlV</i>	TAN04HA	B	0.600
<i>Rod TiAlV</i>	TAN04HA	C	0.548
<i>Rod TiAlV</i>	TAN06HA	A	0.658
<i>Rod TiAlV</i>	TAN06HA	B	0.590
<i>Rod TiAlV</i>	TAN06HA	C	0.752
<i>Gyroid TiAlV</i>	TAN04HA	A	3.040
<i>Gyroid TiAlV</i>	TAN04HA	B	3.010
<i>Gyroid TiAlV</i>	TAN04HA	C	3.340
<i>Gyroid TiAlV</i>	TAN06HA	A	3.770
<i>Gyroid TiAlV</i>	TAN06HA	B	3.880
<i>Gyroid TiAlV</i>	TAN06HA	C	3.870

The silver concentration values in extract of the coatings on the rod are similar to those measured by the authors in extract of the coatings on titanium plates [20, 21].

4. Discussion

4.1 Microstructure

The microstructure of the sol-gel-coated titanium and Ti6Al4V alloy samples exhibited distinct characteristics depending on the substrate geometry and coating composition. Un [28] found through extensive experimental research that the composition of the sol, dip-coating conditions and thermal treatment can significantly affect the properties of sol-gel coatings. The stiffness discrepancy (better bonding) between the implant and the bone tissue can be addressed by making porous materials. In addition, the generated pores could improve bone ingrowth towards the interior of the implant (with an optimal pore size) [29].

The machined wrought Ti6Al4V alloy rod displayed a relatively uniform and smooth surface after mechanical grinding and ultrasonic cleaning. Following sol-gel coating and thermal treatment, the coatings demonstrated good adhesion with minimal cracking, ensuring homogeneous coverage. Hydroxyapatite (HA) and silver (Ag) particles were evenly distributed across the surface, and no significant delamination was observed. Sol penetration was optimal, resulting in a stable and adherent coating.

In contrast, the 3D-printed gyroid structures presented greater challenges in achieving homogeneous coatings due to their complex geometry. Although the coatings adhered well to the substrate, significant cracking was observed, likely due to uneven sol flow over the intricate surface during dip-coating and subsequent thermal expansion stresses. However, the coatings maintained good adhesion, and their bioactive and antibacterial functionalities were retained. The silver nanoparticle distribution was less uniform compared to the rod samples, which could influence the localized antibacterial

performance. The gyroid structures, with their highly porous architecture, provided an increased surface area, potentially enhancing interactions with biological environments.

The 3D-printed dodethick structures presented an even more intricate surface morphology, composed of overlapping grid layers and embedded beads. The coatings on these structures exhibited localized cracking, particularly around the beads, but maintained excellent adhesion. The sol effectively penetrated through the scaffold to the underlying plate, indicating that the viscosity was optimized for such geometries. The micro-HA and nano-Ag additives were distributed throughout the surface, although achieving homogeneity was challenging. Cross-sectional analysis confirmed that the coatings successfully penetrated the lattice, effectively covering the complex internal surfaces. Interestingly, fewer cracks were observed within the inner regions of the dodethick scaffolds, suggesting that surface curvature and confined geometries influenced stress distribution during thermal treatment.

The study demonstrated that sol-gel coatings effectively conformed to different titanium-based substrates, but substrate geometry significantly impacted coating homogeneity and integrity. While smooth surfaces such as the machined rod facilitated uniform coatings with minimal defects, complex 3D-printed structures, especially gyroid and dodethick designs, required careful optimization of sol viscosity and deposition techniques to minimize cracking. Future work should focus on refining coating application methods, potentially incorporating multi-step layering or modified drying protocols to enhance coating uniformity and mechanical stability across highly structured surfaces.

4.2 Properties

Sol-gel coatings applied to titanium and Ti6Al4V alloy substrates exhibited variations in bioactivity, antibacterial properties, and adhesion, depending on substrate geometry and coating composition.

Coatings on the machined wrought Ti6Al4V alloy rod demonstrated outstanding adhesion, with minimal particle detachment observed in the tape test. This strong adhesion can be attributed to the rod's relatively smooth surface, which facilitated uniform coating deposition and strong interfacial bonding during thermal treatment. Milella [30] prepared titanium sol-gel coatings containing HA and found cracks on their surface after firing. The cracks do not influence the mechanical and adhesive properties (by tensile test) of the coating. In contrast, the 3D-printed gyroid and dodethick structures maintained good adhesion, although some surface irregularities and cracks were present. The coatings adhered well even to the highly porous and intricate lattice structures, indicating their potential for biomedical applications. However, the gyroid and dodethick samples exhibited more pronounced cracking, likely due to internal stresses introduced during drying and firing by their complex geometries.

In vitro simulated body fluid (SBF) tests assessed coating bioactivity, confirming that HA-containing coatings (TAN04HA and TAN06HA) promoted fast hydroxyapatite formation. Nano- and micro-HA particles facilitated the precipitation of a thick hydroxyapatite layer on the coated surfaces, mimicking the mineralization process necessary for effective bone integration. The machined rod and gyroid structures showed extensive apatite deposition, demonstrating their bioactive nature. The dodethick scaffold with HA coatings also displayed significant hydroxyapatite precipitation, with the coating penetrating the scaffold structure's complexity. In contrast, the T coating (without HA or

Ag additives) showed limited bioactivity, highlighting the importance of HA in promoting osteointegration. Montenero [31] found that the presence of cracks in T coating could be a favourable centre for small (slow) hydroxyapatite precipitation. Li [32] confirms that sol-gel coating containing HA powder can stimulate the formation of hydroxyapatite from solution (in vitro, SBF) and improve the bonding of the sol-gel prepared titania with bone (in vivo, mature female goats).

Antibacterial tests against *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) revealed a strong bactericidal effect for silver-containing coatings (TAN04HA and TAN06HA). Both coatings exhibited near-100% antibacterial efficiency within 24 hours, confirming the ability of Ag-doped sol-gel layers to prevent bacterial colonization. The machined rod and gyroid structures showed complete bacterial elimination, while the dodethick scaffold coatings demonstrated a 99.7% antibacterial effect. This antibacterial performance is attributed to the release of silver ions, which effectively disrupted bacterial membranes. However, the T coating (without Ag) exhibited only a 44% reduction in bacterial growth, confirming silver's primary role as the antibacterial agent. The titania coatings show antibacterial effect and the silver content improves significantly this behaviour [33]. Mo [34] explains that Ag^+ inhibits the DNA synthesis with direct binding on the bacterial DNA. Ag^+ also adsorbs the protein on the surface of the bacterial membrane.

Cytotoxicity tests using L929 fibroblast cells confirmed that most coatings were non-toxic, with the exception of gyroid samples containing the highest Ag concentration (TAN06HA), which exhibited reduced cell viability. The cytotoxic response was linked to higher silver ion release, approximately five times greater in gyroid samples compared to the rod substrates. This suggests that substrate geometry influences Ag release dynamics, with the more porous gyroid structure facilitating increased ion diffusion. Despite this, the TAN04HA coating, containing a lower Ag concentration, remained non-toxic while providing antibacterial protection, identifying it as the most promising formulation for biomedical applications. Massaro [35] and Ramires [36] tested the behavior of sol-gel coatings with different concentrations of hydroxyapatite powder towards cells by contact and non-contact tests (MG63 cells). The coatings were non-toxic and allowed the differentiation of cells, stimulating the expression of some peculiar osteoblast biochemical markers: APC, collagen and osteocalcin production. The coatings showed the bioactivity as well by precipitation of the needle-like calcium phosphate. *In vitro* and *in vivo* test showed better performance of sol-gel coatings containing bioactive elements (hydroxyapatite, bioglass) with respect to uncoated titanium (ALP, collagen and higher removal torque, larger bone-implant contact area) [37].

The combination of bioactive hydroxyapatite and antibacterial silver in sol-gel coatings provided a multifunctional surface modification suitable for orthopaedic and dental implants. The coatings adhered successfully to different titanium-based substrates, exhibited excellent bioactivity, and provided strong antibacterial effects. However, the extent of cracking in the coatings depended on substrate geometry, with gyroid and dodethick samples showing higher susceptibility to defects. Additionally, silver release must be carefully optimized to balance antibacterial effectiveness and cytocompatibility. Future studies should explore alternative deposition techniques or layered coating approaches to enhance uniformity and mechanical stability while maintaining the beneficial properties of sol-gel coatings.

5. Conclusions

The sol-gel coatings applied to Ti6Al4V alloy substrates exhibited variations in bioactivity, antibacterial properties, and adhesion, depending on substrate geometry and coating composition.

Coatings on the machined wrought Ti6Al4V alloy rod demonstrated outstanding adhesion, with minimal particle detachment observed in the tape test. This strong adhesion can be attributed to the rod's relatively smooth surface, which facilitated uniform coating deposition and strong interfacial bonding during thermal treatment. The sol-gel coatings were successfully prepared in the porous 3D printed structures. The coatings in the 3D-printed gyroid and dodethick structures showed good adhesion, although some surface irregularities and cracks were present. The coatings adhered well even to the highly porous and intricate lattice structures, indicating their potential for biomedical applications. However, the gyroid and dodethick samples exhibited more pronounced cracking, likely due to internal stresses introduced during drying and firing by their complex geometries.

In vitro simulated body fluid (SBF) tests assessed coating bioactivity, confirming that HA-containing coatings (TAN04HA and TAN06HA) promoted hydroxyapatite formation. Nano- and micro-HA particles facilitated the precipitation of a thick hydroxyapatite layer on the coated surfaces, mimicking the mineralization process necessary for effective bone integration. The machined rod and gyroid structures showed extensive apatite deposition, demonstrating their bioactive nature. The dodethick scaffold with HA coatings also displayed significant hydroxyapatite precipitation, with the coating penetrating the scaffold structure's complexity. In contrast, the T coating (without HA or Ag additives) showed limited bioactivity, highlighting the importance of HA in promoting osteointegration.

Antibacterial tests against *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) revealed a strong bactericidal effect for silver-containing coatings (TAN04HA and TAN06HA). Both coatings exhibited near-100% antibacterial efficiency within 24 hours, confirming the ability of Ag-doped sol-gel layers to prevent bacterial colonization. The machined rod and gyroid structures showed complete bacterial elimination, while the dodethick scaffold coatings demonstrated a 99.7% antibacterial effect. This antibacterial performance is attributed to the release of silver ions, which effectively disrupted bacterial membranes. However, the T coating (without Ag) exhibited only a 44% reduction in bacterial growth, confirming silver's primary role as the antibacterial agent.

Cytotoxicity tests using L929 cells (murine fibroblasts) confirmed that most coatings were non-toxic, with the exception of gyroid samples containing the highest Ag concentration (TAN06HA), which exhibited reduced cell viability. The cytotoxic response was linked to higher silver ion release, approximately five times greater in gyroid samples compared to the rod substrates. This suggests that substrate geometry influences Ag release dynamics, with the more porous gyroid structure facilitating increased ion diffusion. Despite this, the TAN04HA coating, containing a lower Ag concentration, remained non-toxic while providing antibacterial protection, identifying it as the most promising formulation for biomedical applications.

The combination of bioactive hydroxyapatite and antibacterial silver in sol-gel coatings provided a multifunctional surface modification suitable for orthopaedic and dental implants. The coatings adhered successfully to different titanium-based substrates,

exhibited excellent bioactivity, and provided strong antibacterial effects. However, the extent of cracking in the coatings depended on substrate geometry, with gyroid and dodecahedral samples showing higher susceptibility to defects. Additionally, silver release must be carefully optimized to balance antibacterial effectiveness and cytocompatibility. Future studies should explore alternative deposition techniques or layered coating approaches to enhance uniformity and mechanical stability while maintaining the beneficial properties of sol-gel coatings.

Data availability

The data will be available in the Zenodo repository at the following link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15411651>

Declaration of the competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interest or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Anna Knaislova: Writing – original draft; review & editing. **Diana Horkavcova:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Eva Jablonska:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Dalibor Vojtěch:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing.

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Figure captions:

- Fig. 1. The scheme of the experiment
- Fig. 2 Machined wrought TiAl6V4 alloy rod
- Fig. 3 3D printed TiAl6V4 alloy gyroid
- Fig. 4 3D printed titanium dodethick
- Fig. 5 Dip-coater and magnetic stirrer
- Fig. 6 Holders of the samples
- Fig. 7 Microstructure of the samples after cleaning: a, b) the machined wrought rod after mechanical treatment and subsequent cleaning; c), d) gyroid 5mm - 3D; e, f, g, h) dodethick 3D
- Fig. 8 Microstructure of the machined wrought rod after firing: a, b) T coating; c, d) TAN04HA coating; e, f) TAN06HA coating
- Fig. 9 Microstructure of the Ti6Al4V gyroid 3D after firing: a, b) T coating; c, d) TAN04HA coating; e, f) TAN06HA coating
- Fig. 10 Microstructure of the Ti dodethick 3D with T coating after firing
- Fig. 11 Microstructure of the Ti dodethick 3D with TAN04HA coating after firing
- Fig. 12 Microstructure of the Ti dodethick 3D with TAN06HA coating after firing
- Fig. 13 Microstructure of Ti - dodethick (3D printing; grid: 1.35): T coating after firing – cross section
- Fig. 14 Microstructure of Ti - dodethick (3D printing; grid: 1.35): TAN04HA coating after firing – cross section

Fig. 15 Microstructure of Ti - dodethick (3D printing; grid: 1.35): TAN06HA coating after firing – cross section

Fig. 16 The adhesion of the coatings of the machined wrought rod after firing: a) TAN04HA; b) TAN06HA

Fig. 17 Microstructure of the machined wrought rod after *in vitro* test in SBF: a, b) T coating; c, d) TAN04HA coating; e, f) TAN06HA coating

Fig. 18 Microstructure of the gyroid after *in vitro* test in SBF: a, b) T coating; c, d) TAN04HA coating; e, f) TAN06HA coating

Fig. 19 Microstructure of Ti - dodethick (3D printing; grid: 1.35) with T coating after *in vitro test* in SBF

Fig. 20 Microstructure of Ti - dodethick (3D printing; grid: 1.35) with TAN04HA coating after *in vitro test* in SBF

Fig. 21 Microstructure of Ti - dodethick (3D printing; grid: 1.35) with TAN06HA coating after *in vitro test* in SBF

Fig. 22 Number of colonies of survived bacteria *E. coli* after 24 hour antibacterial test

Fig. 23 Relative metabolic activity (%) of L929 cells (mouse fibroblasts) after 24 h of interaction and concentration of the silver in the extracts ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$).

Table captions:

Table 1 Antibacterial effect [%] of the coatings against *E. coli* after 24-hour antibacterial test (average of four values)

Table 2 The silver content in the extracts